

Impact Of Core Self-Evaluation And Humor Style On Psychological Well-Being Of Individuals

Malik Mureed Hussain, Muhammad Tahir Khalily, Tariq Mehmood Bhuttah, Abdul Sattar Ghaffari

ArticleInfo

ArticleHistory

Received:

January 01,2021

Accepted:

March 03,2021

Keywords:

Core Self-Evaluation,
Humor Style, Well-Being.

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.4991535

Abstract

The present study aims to explore the individual's psychological well-being of individuals in the context of core self-evaluation and humor style. The sample consisted of 132 students with age ranges between 16 to 27 years from three different educational institutes. For the data collection, three scales including Psychological well-being scale, Core Self-evaluation scale and Humor Style Questionnaire short version were used. The results indicate that Core self-evaluation and humor style can impact on psychological well-being of adult people. People who are emotionally stable will score high on core self-evaluation and high emotional stability with adaptive humor style will cause high ranking of psychological well-being. Low core self-evaluation with maladaptive humor style leads to low psychological well-being in adults. Moreover, demographic variables with respect to gender do not influence psychological well-being and core self-evaluation among individuals. While results indicate that core self-evaluation is inter correlated to psychological wellbeing. Hence, core self-evaluation along with humor style is important in determining psychological well-being.

Introduction

Generally, analysts have considered humor style as solely adaptive in its nature (Cann et.al, 2010). Martin et.al (2003) recognized four different humor styles that individuals routinely utilize. The affiliative and self-enhancing humor styles are advantageous to self and others, whereas aggressive and self-defeating humor styles are negative or unpleasant to self and others. Martin et.al (2003) model has enormously explained the multifaceted and frequently strange connection between humor style and personal well-being. It has uncovered that contingent upon how it is utilized in everyday routine and humor is able to emphatically or contrarily identify with a large assortment of indications of mental well-being (Cann& Collette, 2014).

Individuals with affiliative humor style utilize humor to accomplish relational or societal gains. They employ humor for engaging others to improve the societal relations. Individuals with self-enhancing humor style employ humor for personal satisfaction .They keep up a humorous point of view. In this regard, self-enhancing humor is firmly identified with adapting comical inclination (Cann et al., 2010).

Individuals with aggressive humor style employ humor for relational connections all the more remunerating for the self as well as other people, they also used humor as a method for censuring or controlling others. They exhibit their prevalence over others and consider other people's well-being (Martin et al., 2003). Of course, this humor style has been demonstrated to be hindering to relational connections (Cann, Zapata & Davis, 2011). At long last, individuals with self-defeating humor style make jokes about their own shortcomings so as to charm themselves to other people. They employ humor to abstain from defying issues and managing negative emotions (Stieger, Formann, and Burger, 2011).

Since, the idea of humor is both relational and personal and it impacts social collaborations and intrapersonal contemplations as well as sentiments. The Humor Styles Theory (Martin et al., 2003) investigates it more profoundly examining humor for many years and found that all humor styles have many differentiations with each other. All these humor styles have their own specifications regardless they are positive or negative. These humor styles indicate how an individual feel and see to self and others. Usually, the major aim of humor is to get the attention, praise and association of others. Individuals with self-defeating humor style indicate their weakness in humor to get support, attention and rewards from others as well as to avoid problems and negative feelings.

Positive psychology investigation has shown that humor affects an individual's physical and mental well-being (Cann et al., 2010). For instance, humor has appeared to profit those experiencing a few types of cancer or mind, brain problems, and carry relief for those who are near to death (Mak, 2018). The effectiveness of humor on mental and physical well-being is indicated by the work of Norman Cousins (1979) published with entitled *Anatomy of an illness as perceived by the patient: Reflections on healing and regeneration* which mentioned

humor as a kind of medicine for the treatment of physical diseases. Cousins also treated their terminal degenerative tissue disease with the use of humor and gradually replaced the pain killer medicines. His work crafted by other significant analysts that hardened the mission to get humor and its relation to body and psyche. There have been clashing hypotheses with respect to characterizing and developing the structure squares of humor. Regarding human sciences, humor started as a medicinal term, utilized by the Greeks to portray the four natural liquids that directed positive or negative practices (dark or yellow bile, blood and mucus) (Raskin, 2008). Freud's hypothesis of optimistic feeling was particularly significant, recommending humor the most important portrayal of the oblivious psyche (Newirth, 2006). Humor is not currently comprehended to exclusively be a societal connection, however, a significant intrapersonal collaboration too. The individuals may exercise humor to associate with others and to approve themselves. This is a fundamental segment of connection. (Polimeni& Reiss, 2006). With regards to this point of view of humor, McGhee (1979) guessed that one's quality is the thing that directed what he named a "comical inclination". All the more explicitly, humor was fundamental to human improvement. The youngsters were observed as intrinsically fun loving, until socialization changed this degree of reality versus liveliness. McGhee's hypothesis incorporates ideas, for example discovering humor in regular daily existence, utilizing humor under pressure and the delight in humor. In this regard, humor has been characterized as an adapting or protection component and as an inborn characteristic or personality (Raskin, 2008). These facts confirm that humor contains these components somehow or another. This supports the Humor Styles Theory. Martin et al. (2003) proposed the Humor Styles Theory which fixated on the conviction that humor has both dark and bright capacities. Humor is viewed as genuinely steady ingredient for the duration of grown-up life. when people tend to utilize humor in a reliable manner. In particular, four styles of humor hypothesis incorporate two positive (affiliative and self-enhancing) and two negative (aggressive and self-defeating) humor styles and was built by analyzing different theories of humor to formulate a legitimate 2x2 model.

Positive humor styles are derived from prior hypotheses of humor as adaptive strategy and beneficial for mental well-being and for sentimental satisfaction, good health and social self-regard (Yue et al., 2014). Affiliative humor incorporates practical witting and playful joking. Usually, it is utilized to entertain others and to mitigate pressure. It is also used to develop good relational connections. It is usually considered a non-aggressive and pretty. Martin et al. (2003) additionally estimated this humor to be connected to liveliness like McGhee's (1979) comical inclination. Self-enhancing humor used to face calamity and stressors in existence with a positive and humorous point of view like Freud's perspective on a solid protection component (Martin et al., 2003). Self-enhancing humor is more intra-personal and permits an individual to face the life problems in a witty way and manufacturing it in a simpler manner to control bad feelings. According to Martin, et al. (2003), "My humorous point of view shields me from getting excessively annoyed or discouraged about things". It is likewise critical to take note of those previous speculations of humor as a way of dealing with stress would apply to self-enhancing humor.

However, a few prior hypotheses have appeared that humor could be utilized to protect oneself from negative reaction from others and to protect one's own well-being. Humor in negative manner could be benevolent or even detrimental to one's well-being and could lead to neuroticism, social clashes, melancholia and suicide tendency (Schermer et al., 2013). Humor in negative manners can cause difficulties in social relations and can develop feelings of insufficient self-regard and misery (Frewen et al., 2008). On the other hand, aggressive humor incorporates threatening as well as discourteous banter. It is utilized to compromise or control others by developing feeling them inferior and is seen as factious and unacceptable. Self-defeating humor incorporates considering one's self inferior to make joke. This humor is utilized to pick up endorsement commencing others and to stay away from one's own negative emotions (Martin et al., 2003). This is especially intriguing as it is proposed to be identified with discouragement or potentially nervousness and passionate poverty (Martin et al., 2003). It is advised that humor styles which are considered rude or belittle by others and consistent on the content of self-regard leads to negative feelings about self and distorted self-image. Similarly such humor styles also cause hindrance in developing appropriate social relations.

It is important to comprehend the employments of these humor styles while comprehending the individual and social outcomes related with them.

Judge et al. (2004) have indicated that individuals who evaluate themselves in a positive manner in different situations, they have positive image about their capabilities and worth, motivation (Erez& Judge, 2001) and performance (Judge, et.al, 2003) and themselves more happy and satisfied with life and work (Judge & Bono, 2001). Core self-evaluations (CSE) are conceptualized as the recognition about one's own worth and capacity as individuals (Judge, 1998). CSE includes four lower-order characteristics. The principal attribute for the CSE is self-esteem which is a general examination of one's self-worth (Rosenberg, 2015). The other is self-efficacy which is an assessment of one's capacity to effectively play out a wide scope of errands (Bandura, 1977). Emotional stability or low neuroticism, the third CSE quality, is characterized as the inclination to feel quiet and secure (Eysenck, 1990). The last characteristic is locus of control which is the conviction that occasions throughout one's life comes because of one's own activities as opposed by destiny or incredible others (Rotter,

1966). As per CSE hypothesis, these four qualities consolidate to clarify a person's worldwide judgment of the worth that they have as an individual (Judge, Locke, & Durham, 1997).

Judge et al. (2010) have stated that these four characteristics make a complex element known as core self-evaluation. Judge et al. (2012) further define core self-evaluation as an individual's ability to evaluate one's own capabilities and worth.

Life brims with difficulties so, having what it takes important to address these difficulties can prompt a more joyful life and a more prominent feeling of well-being. While there are a wide range of abilities that may be valuable in supporting achievement and well-being. A decent comical inclination has frequently been proposed as an individual quality equipped for encouraging the accomplishment of psychological well-being (Martin et al., 2003). Scientists have recognized various procedures through which a decent comical inclination may bolster well-being.

Notwithstanding, encouraging more positive examinations of possible dangers, a decent sense of humor likewise could have a more global effect by taking into more positive viewpoint about oneself and the world (Martin et al., 2003). A decent sense of humor might resemble a focal point through which the world is seen. For instance, Kuiper, et al., (1992) found that higher scores on different measurements of sense of humor were related with higher fulfillment with the roles individuals in their lives. A superior sense of humor related to higher positive influence even as either positive or negative life occasions were competent at more elevated levels. The global point of view on life is upheld by the research announced by Ruch and Carrell (1998). They have demonstrated that a decent sense of humor is related with sparkle as a characteristic, just as a state. These affiliations recommend that a decent sense of humor may upgrade different qualities that may fill in as assets when confronting difficulties.

In developing a model concentrating on constructive individual qualities, instead of on pathologies, Peterson & Seligman (2012) have proposed a lot of ideals dependent on the nearness of various character qualities. They recognized 24 character qualities that bolstered six expansive ethics. These character qualities and temperance were accepted to impact how fulfilled and satisfied people would feel with their lives. Humor was incorporated as a character quality that assisted with supporting the prudence of greatness. In their model, amazing quality speaks to those qualities that take into account discovering importance and feeling associated with the more extensive universe. Humor, as character quality, was characterized as preferring to joke and chuckle and imparting humor to other people. More significant levels of character qualities were thought to be related with more note-worthy life fulfillment (Peterson & Seligman, 2012). In two investigations including huge examples across three nations, humor, evaluated as a character quality was decidedly identified with life fulfillment and other prosperity pointers (Peterson, Ruch, Beermann, Park, and Seligman, 2007; Ruch et al., 2010). Along these lines, apparently a decent sense of humor can give the establishment to a more constructive perspective and more note-worthy individual quality, empowering connects to prosperity.

Materials & Methods:

Sample consisted of 132 individuals from different educational institutes of Multan city. The age range of respondents was 16 to 27 years with educational level from intermediate to graduate. Male respondents were 70 and females respondents were 62. Data collection was done by utilizing convenience sampling. Booklets containing three questionnaires i.e. Core self-evaluation scale, Humor Styles Questionnaire and Psychological Well-being scale were distributed and then taken back from participants.

Instruments

Core Self -Evaluation Scale (CSES)

The scale was designed by Judge et al. (2003). It consisted of 12 items with 5 point Likert Scale with no subscales. The scale covers four aspects of personality namely self-esteem, generalized self-efficacy, locus of control and emotional stability specifically neuroticism under one heading of core self-evaluation. High scores indicate positive core self-evaluation and low score indicate negative core self-evaluation.

Humor Styles Questionnaire (HSQ)

The questionnaire was designed by Martin, et al., (2003). This scale assesses four different humor styles, two are primarily other directed: with aggressive humor involving, affiliative humor, self-directed and self-enhancing. It is a 32 items questionnaire and eight items assess each humor style.

Psychological Well-being Scale (PWS)

Psychological well-being scale is developed by Gough (1987). It is a 38 items true-false questionnaire. The scale was mostly used to evaluate the psychological well-being of individuals. This is 38 items true, false scale where true response has 1 score and false response has 0 score.

Results:

Table 1: Correlation between core self-evaluation, psychological well-being, adaptive humor style, and aggressive humor style

Variables	Mean ± SD	1	2	3	4
CSE	39.91±5.10	1	.415**	.421**	-.211**
PWB	19.65±4.53		-	.502**	-.315**
AdHS	40.22±3.21			-	-.192**
AgHS	38.19±2.99				1

Where CSE: Core self-evaluation, PWB: Psychological well-being, AdHS: Adaptive Humor Style and AgHS: Aggressive Humor Style

The table 1 shows the results of correlation between core self-evaluation, psychological well-being, adaptive humor style, and aggressive humor style. From the results, we conclude that core self-evaluation, psychological well-being, adaptive humor style, and aggressive humor style are significantly correlated with each other.

Table 2: Regression analysis for psychological well-being as outcome while core self-evaluation, adaptive humor style and aggressive humor style as independent variables

Variable	Unstandardized		Standardized	t	p-value
	Coefficient		Coefficient		
	β	S.E(β)	β		
Constant	.699	.062		10.790	.000
CSE	.028	.003	.021	9.333	.000
AdHS	.074	.018	.054	4.111	.000
AgHS	-.049	.004	-.038	-12.250	.000

Where CSE: Core self-evaluation, PWB: Psychological well-being, AdHS: Adaptive Humor Style and AgHS: Aggressive Humor Style

Table 2 shows result of regression analysis for psychological wellbeing as outcome while core self-evaluation, adaptive humor style and aggressive humor style as independent variables. From the results, we conclude that core self-evaluation and adaptive humor style have significantly positive impact on psychological well-being while aggressive humor style has significantly negative impact on psychological well-being.

Table 3: Mean standard deviation t and p value of core self-evaluation, psychological well-being, adaptive humor style, and aggressive humor style in males and females

Scales	Groups	N	Mean	SD	t	P
CSE	Male	70	38.31	6.63	-.39	.351
	Female	62	39.68	3.87		
PWB	Male	70	19.03	4.46	-.30	.381
	Female	62	19.27	4.60		
AdHS	Male	70	39.45	5.21	.58	.282
	Female	62	38.95	4.65		
AgHS	Male	70	40.05	4.87	.34	.368
	Female	62	39.78	4.22		

Where CSE: Core self-evaluation, PWB: Psychological well-being, AdHS: Adaptive Humor Style and AgHS: Aggressive Humor Style

Table shows 3 the comparisons of core self-evaluation, psychological well-being, adaptive humor style, and aggressive humor style between male and female respondents. From the results, we conclude that there is no significant difference in the levels of core self-evaluation, psychological well-being, adaptive humor style, and aggressive humor style.

Table 4: One Way Analysis of Variance on Core Self-Evaluation and Psychological Well-being among different age groups.

Variables	Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	P
CSE	Between Group	400.23	3	133.41	7.471	.000***
	Within Group	2285.74	128	17.86		
	Group Total	2685.97	131			
PWB	Between Group	380.42	3	126.81	8.176	.000***
	Within Group	1985.80	128	15.51		
	Group Total	3085.72	131			

Above table 4 shows the results of one way analysis of variance for core self-evaluation and psychological well-being among different age groups. Form the results we conclude that there is significant difference between the levels of core self-evaluation and psychological well-being with p-values .000 and .000 respectively.

Discussion:

Psychological well-being has widely studied in different dimensions. The present study has tried to introduce a new area of study by investigating the Core Self-Evaluation and Humor Styles of individuals and checking their impact on Psychological Well-being. Core Self-Evaluation is basically the trait that defines how an individual judges himself or herself in terms of abilities and emotional control. Humor Style determines how individuals take different events occurring to them in terms of fun, recreation and laughter. Both these things seem to influence psychological well-being of individuals.

The present study focuses on determining whether a specific Core Self-evaluation level along with specific humor style has had an impact on psychological well-being or not. Combining the Core Self-evaluation level along with specific Humor Style and making different groups for determining different effects on psychological well-being level, makes four groups: Positive Core Self-evaluation with adaptive humor style, Positive Core Self-evaluation with maladaptive humor style, Negative Core Self-evaluation with adaptive humor style, and Negative Core Self-evaluation with maladaptive humor style.

Results indicated in table 1 show that Core Self-evaluation along with adaptive humor style is significantly correlated with negative Core Self-evaluation and maladaptive humor style. It is suggested that mean difference between two groups is highest and is 4.35. The second group is found to be correlated with no such group while third group was significantly correlated with the first group and the fourth group was found significantly correlated with first group while fourth group was having negative core self-evaluation and adaptive humor style. The mean difference between the groups was 2.70. These findings are supported by the findings of Cann, & Collette (2014) and Cann, et.al (2010).

Kuiper, Grim Shaw, Leite, and Krish (2004) found that low adaptive humor style is associated with lower well-being and high adaptive humor style is related to better well-being including competencies in life especially with coping process. On the other hand, the maladaptive style was positively correlated depression, anxiety and negative self-competencies.

Previous research more specifically shows that the self-schema of emotions describes psychological well-being which depends on an individual's level of endorsement of self-evaluative standards. These standards form the primary evaluative component in an individual's self-schema, which he or she uses to guide, assess and integrate his or her life experiences. Greater endorsement of negative self-evaluative standard results in poorer psychological well-being i.e higher level of depression and lower self-esteem. The greater endorsement of positive self-evaluative standards results in enhances well-being i.e lower levels of depression and higher self-esteem (Krish& Kuiper (2000). In this conceptual framework, the humor styles can be considered as one set of behavioral tendencies that are commonly expressed in social interactions (Campbell, et al., 2008).

Thus, Core self-evaluation and humor styles influence the psychological well-being of individuals. Hence, first hypothesis is being supported in the light of results and previous research.

The correlation between Core self-evaluation and psychological well-being was found to be significant i.e. 0.05. Hence, the two variables are inter correlated. Krish& Kuiper (2002) have presented the self-evaluation affects psychological wellbeing in such way that high self-evaluation leads to enhanced wellbeing while low self-evaluation leads toward lower wellbeing. So levels of Core self-evaluation high or low cause the psychological well-being to lower or higher accordingly.

Findings also indicated that when the core self-evaluation of males and females was being checked, there was no significant difference observed as indicated by table no 3. Probably, it was because of cultural influence of less difference in male and female. Self-Evaluation, if males are being encouraged in society having high self-esteem, internal locus of control, generalized self-efficacy and having lower level of neuroticism. Then in our culture females are also being encouraged for having same qualities in order to lead better life possibilities. Similarly, when the psychological well-being among adults was focused to measure in males and females differently, no significant differences were being found. Humor styles among males and females also show no differences. Many males report high score on affiliative humor style along with aggressive humor style while many females report high score on aggressive humor style than affiliative humor style. This shows that humor style is not influenced by gender differences. Especially, differences are found to be significant with regard to any of the three variables including core self-evaluation, humor style and psychological well-being.

References:

- Cann, A., & Collette, C. (2014). Sense of humor, stable affect, and psychological well-being. *Europe's Journal of Psychology*, 10(3), 464-479.
- Cann, A., Stilwell, K., & Taku, K. (2010). Humor styles, positive personality and health. *Europe's Journal of Psychology*, 6(3), 213-235.
- Cann, A., Davis, H. B., & Zapata, C. L. (2011). Humor styles and relationship satisfaction in dating couples: Perceived versus self-reported humor styles as predictors of satisfaction. *Humor*, 24(1), 1-20.
- Erez, A., & Judge, T. A. (2001). Relationship of core self-evaluations to goal setting, motivation, and performance. *Journal of applied psychology*, 86(6), 1270.
- Eysenck, H. J. (1990). Biological dimensions of personality.

- Judge, T. A., Ilies, R., & Zhang, Z. (2012). Genetic influences on core self-evaluations, job satisfaction, and work stress: A behavioral genetics mediated model. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, 117(1), 208-220.
- Judge, T. A., Piccolo, R. F., Podsakoff, N. P., Shaw, J. C., & Rich, B. L. (2010). The relationship between pay and job satisfaction: A meta-analysis of the literature. *Journal of vocational behavior*, 77(2), 157-167.
- Judge, T. A., & Bono, J. E. (2001). Relationship of core self-evaluations traits—self-esteem, generalized self-efficacy, locus of control, and emotional stability—with job satisfaction and job performance: A meta-analysis. *Journal of applied Psychology*, 86(1), 80.
- Judge, T. A., Erez, A., Bono, J. E., & Thoresen, C. J. (2003). The core self-evaluations scale: Development of a measure. *Personnel psychology*, 56(2), 303-331.
- Judge, T. A. (1997). The dispositional causes of job satisfaction: A core evaluations approach. *Research in organizational behavior*, 19, 151-188.
- Judge, T. A., Locke, E. A., Durham, C. C., & Kluger, A. N. (1998). Dispositional effects on job and life satisfaction: the role of core evaluations. *Journal of applied psychology*, 83(1), 17.
- Judge, T. A., Van Vianen, A. E., & De Pater, I. E. (2004). Emotional stability, core self-evaluations, and job outcomes: A review of the evidence and an agenda for future research. *Human performance*, 17(3), 325-346.
- Kirsh, G. A., & Kuiper, N. A. (2002). Individualism and relatedness themes in the context of depression, gender, and a self-schema model of emotion. *Canadian Psychology/Psychologie canadienne*, 43(2), 76.
- Kuiper, N. A., Martin, R. A., & Dance, K. A. (1992). Sense of humour and enhanced quality of life. *Personality and individual differences*, 13(12), 1273-1283.
- Mak, W., & Sörensen, S. (2018). Are humor styles of people with dementia linked to greater purpose in life?. *The Gerontologist*, 58(5), 835-842.
- Martin, R. A., Puhlik-Doris, P., Larsen, G., Gray, J., & Weir, K. (2003). Individual differences in uses of humor and their relation to psychological well-being: Development of the Humor Styles Questionnaire. *Journal of research in personality*, 37(1), 48-75.
- McGhee, P. E., & Pistolesi, E. (1979). *Humor: Its origin and development*. San Francisco: WH Freeman.
- Newirth, J. (2006). Jokes and their relation to the unconscious: Humor as a fundamental emotional experience. *Psychoanalytic Dialogues*, 16(5), 557-571.
- Peterson, C., & Seligman, M. E. (2012). *Character Strengths and Virtues: A Handbook and Classification* (New York: American Psychological Association & Oxford University Press, 2004). *Reflective Practice: Formation and Supervision in Ministry*, 32.
- Peterson, C., Ruch, W., Beermann, U., Park, N., & Seligman, M. E. (2007). Strengths of character, orientations to happiness, and life satisfaction. *The journal of positive psychology*, 2(3), 149-156.
- Polimeni, J., & Reiss, J. P. (2006). The first joke: Exploring the evolutionary origins of humor. *Evolutionary psychology*, 4(1), 147470490600400129.
- Raskin, V. (Ed.). (2008). *The primer of humor research* (Vol. 8). Walter de Gruyter.
- Rosenberg, M. (2015). *Society and the adolescent self-image*. Princeton university press.
- Rotter, J. B. (1966). Generalized expectancies for internal versus external control of reinforcement. *Psychological monographs: General and applied*, 80(1), 1.
- Ruch, W., & Carrell, A. (1998). Trait cheerfulness and the sense of humour. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 24(4), 551-558.
- Ruch, W., Proyer, R. T., Harzer, C., Park, N., Peterson, C., & Seligman, M. E. (2010). Values in action inventory of strengths (VIA-IS): adaptation and validation of the German version and the development of a peer-rating form. *Journal of individual differences*, 31(3), 138.
- Schermer, J. A., Martin, R. A., Martin, N. G., Lynskey, M., & Vernon, P. A. (2013). The general factor of personality and humor styles. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 54(8), 890-893.
- Stieger, S., Formann, A. K., & Burger, C. (2011). Humor styles and their relationship to explicit and implicit self-esteem. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 50(5), 747-750.
- Tucker, R. P., Judah, M. R., O'Keefe, V. M., Mills, A. C., Lechner, W. V., Davidson, C. L., ... & Wingate, L. R. (2013). Humor styles impact the relationship between symptoms of social anxiety and depression. *Personality and individual differences*, 55(7), 823-827.
- Yue, X. D., Liu, K. W. Y., Jiang, F., & Hiranandani, N. A. (2014). Humor styles, self-esteem, and subjective happiness. *Psychological reports*, 115(2), 517-525.
- Zhang, J., Wu, Q., Miao, D., Yan, X., & Peng, J. (2014). The impact of core self-evaluations on job satisfaction: The mediator role of career commitment. *Social Indicators Research*, 116(3), 809-822.

AuthorInformation

Malik Mureed Hussain

Director & Associate Professor, Multan
Postgraduate College, Multan, Pakistan

Tariq Mehmood Bhuttah

Assistant professor (Education), Humanities and
Social Sciences Department at KhwajaFareed
University of engineering and information
technology, Rahimyar Khan, 64200 Pakistan.

Muhammad Tahir Khalily

Professor of Psychology at International Islamic
University, Islamabad, Pakistan

Abdul SattarGhaffari

***(Corresponding Author)**
Zhongtai Securities Institute for Financial
Studies, School of Mathematics, Shandong
University, Jinan, China
